

RESEARCH GAPS IN DEVELOPING A LUNAR SHUTTLE USING HYBRID PROPULSION AND ISRU PROPELLANT PRODUCTION. A. Dabanović¹, M. Haupt², M. Fertig¹, V. Wartemann¹, A. Thakur³, M. Özaslan⁴, S. Scholl⁵, S. Silvestri³ and R. Güttel⁶, ¹Institute of Aerodynamics and Flow Technology, German Aerospace Center (DLR), Lilienthalplatz 7, 38108 Braunschweig, Germany, corresponding author: andrija.dabanovic@dlr.de, ²Institute of Aircraft Design and Lightweight Structures, TU Braunschweig, Braunschweig, Germany, ³Institute of Space Systems, TU Braunschweig, Braunschweig, Germany, ⁴Institute of Physical Chemistry, University of Hamburg, Hamburg, Germany, ⁵Institute for Chemical and Thermal Process Engineering, TU Braunschweig, Braunschweig, Germany, ⁶Institute of Chemical Engineering, University of Ulm, Ulm, Germany.

Introduction: The Moon remains a focus of both scientific and commercial interest. Governmental programmes such as ESA's 2040 strategy and NASA's Artemis initiative illustrate growing investment in lunar exploration, while an increasing number of emerging space-faring nations are already launching missions to the surface. The growing commercial promise is encouraging private companies, which have put forward a number of concepts for reusable, partially crewed lunar landers.

Realising large-scale lunar operations, especially extensive in-situ resource utilisation (ISRU) aimed at cutting Earth-origin resupply flights, requires substantial preparatory work. This includes locating suitable landing and construction sites and building the necessary supporting infrastructure. In this context, a compact, reusable shuttle that can perform crewed and uncrewed transfers between the Lunar Orbital Platform-Gateway (LOP-G) and a prospective lunar base offers a pragmatic, low-risk solution for early logistics and infrastructure development.

Discussion: Preliminary Delta-v analyses for a lunar shuttle that can move a 2.5 t payload between the gateway and a surface base using a HTPB/H₂O₂ propellant combination were performed. To reflect the heavier structural requirements of hybrid-rocket systems, we imposed a structural fraction of at least 20 %. The oxidiser, hydrogen peroxide, is assumed to be refilled on both the surface base and the gateway, thereby halving the mass of oxidiser that must be delivered from Earth. The solid fuel (HTPB) is initially transferred in liquid state to the gateway, where the solid fuel grains are additively manufactured. In later stages, it could be sourced locally through ISRU. From this proposed shuttle concept, six tightly coupled research topics emerge: (1) in-situ H₂O₂ production, (2) H₂O₂ purification, (3) durable decomposition catalyst development, (4) ISRU and additive manufacturing of HTPB fuel, (5) performance and efficiency of the shuttle engine, and (6) design of reusable nozzle structures. Addressing these topics in concert is essential to validate the shuttle concept and to close the identified technology gaps.

Conclusion: The six research topics form the core technical foundation of the proposed reusable lunar shuttle and must be addressed jointly by the consortium. Their strong coupling, for example cata-

lyst performance and oxidiser concentration, directly influence engine's internal ballistics and nozzle thermal management. Because of these interdependencies, progress in any single area cannot be isolated from the others. In particular, all topics influence the overall propulsion efficiency, determining the feasibility of the proposed concept. A coordinated research programme covering all six domains is in preparation in order to close the identified gaps and to validate the shuttle concept. This, in turn, would enable a sustainable, low cost logistics chain between the lunar surface and the gateway, thereby supporting long term lunar exploration.